

Geological and Petrographical study of Montecampione Triassic subvolcanic bodies (Southern Alps, Italy): preliminary geodynamic results

PIETRO ARMIENTI (*), CLAUDIA CORAZZATO (**), GIANLUCA GROPELLI (***),
EMANUELE NATOLI (****) & GIORGIO PASQUARÈ (****)

ABSTRACT

The research began with a geological and structural survey of the Triassic subvolcanic bodies cropping out in the area of Montecampione (Val Camonica-BS, Italy). This study allowed the determination of the main phases of intrusion of these bodies, and new and significant sampling of the magmatic rocks in order to reconstruct the geodynamic framework based on high quality geochemical analyses.

These intrusive bodies, belonging to the «Montecampione group», show a minimum volume of about 1 km³ and could represent a shallow (about 1000 m) magmatic reservoir producing a volcanic area, since we recognised some structures related to probable feeding conduits, and the presence of volcanic sandstones coeval with or little younger than the radiometric age of these intrusions (231±5 Ma).

The subvolcanic bodies can be classified following the terminology of volcanic rocks because of the presence of abundant devitrified groundmass and a vacuolar texture. On the basis of the chemical composition, these subvolcanic rocks can be classified in the alkaline series as trachyandesites to trachytes, although it is not possible to determine the sodic or potassic affinity because of the high fluid circulation.

The study of trace elements, and particularly the pronounced enrichment in LREEs and LILEs, allows us to relate the genesis of these magmas to a back-arc setting associated with the great depths achieved by a subducting slab. Based on the radiometric dating and on the paleogeographical reconstructions available, this geodynamic framework could be related to the subduction of Palaeotethyan oceanic crust during the early phases of the Cimmerian orogeny. The formation of the magmatic bodies constituting the «Montecampione group» emplaced at shallow level can thus be related to magmatic upwelling in the framework of a back-arc with limited extension.

KEY WORDS: *Stratigraphy, Petrography, Geochemistry, Subvolcanic Bodies, Intrusions, Triassic, Permian, Southern Alps, Geodynamics.*

RIASSUNTO

Studio geologico e petrografico dei corpi subvolcanici triasici di Montecampione (BS). Indicazioni preliminari sul quadro geodinamico.

La ricerca è iniziata con un rilevamento geologico e strutturale di dettaglio sui corpi subvolcanici di età triassica affioranti nella zona di Montecampione (Val Camonica-BS, Italia). Questo studio ha

permesso di evidenziare le diverse fasi di intrusione dei corpi e di realizzare un nuovo e significativo campionamento delle rocce magmatiche per ricostruire il quadro geodinamico basato anche su analisi geochimiche di elevata qualità.

Questi corpi intrusivi, appartenenti al «gruppo di Montecampione», hanno un volume minimo di oltre 1 km³ e potrebbero rappresentare una camera magmatica superficiale (circa 1000 m di profondità) relativa a un'area vulcanica, poiché si riconoscono strutture assimilabili a condotti di alimentazione e sono presenti sedimenti terrigeni di origine vulcanica coevi o di poco successivi all'età radiometrica dei corpi intrusivi (231±5 Ma).

Per la classificazione dei corpi subvolcanici si possono usare i termini adottati per le rocce vulcaniche data la presenza di abbondante massa di fondo devetrificata e di una tessitura vacuolare. In base alla composizione chimica le rocce subvolcaniche possono essere classificate nella serie alcalina da trachiandesiti a trachiti, anche se non è possibile determinare l'affinità sodica o potassica a causa dell'elevata circolazione dei fluidi.

Lo studio degli elementi in tracce e, in particolare, un evidente arricchimento anomalo in LILE e LREE permettono di attribuire la genesi di questi magmi a un contesto geodinamico caratterizzato da un ambiente di retroarco con lo *slab* in subduzione a elevata profondità. In base alle datazioni e alle ricostruzioni paleogeografiche sinora presentate, questo quadro geodinamico potrebbe essere relativo alle prime fasi dell'orogenesi Cimmerica con la subduzione della crosta oceanica relativa alla Paleotetide. Quindi la formazione dei corpi magmatici intrusi a bassa profondità che costituiscono il «gruppo di Montecampione» si inquadra nella risalita di magmi in un contesto di retroarco con limitata estensione.

TERMINI CHIAVE: *Stratigrafia, Petrografia, Geochimica, Corpi Subvolcanici, Intrusioni, Triassico, Permiano, Sudalpi-no, Geodinamica.*

INTRODUCTION

In the central Southern Alps, near Montecampione (Val Camonica-BS, Italy), in the area of Monte Muffetto, a set of shallow subvolcanic bodies (mainly laccoliths and sills) intruded a Permian-Lower Triassic sequence. They belong to the volcanic and subvolcanic association cropping out in the Brescian area, described in CASSINIS & ZEZZA (1982) (fig. 1). Radiometric dating (Rb/Sr, whole rock and biotite) of the studied intrusions (231±5 and 226±4 Ma; CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982) places them as part of the Middle or Late Triassic volcanism, widespread through the Southern Alps in two main horizons: Upper Anisian-Lower Ladinian and Ladinian-Carnian/Carnian. Coeval pyroclastic fall layers interbedded in a nearby sedimentary succession (PASQUARÈ & ROSSI, 1965) and the Arenaria di Val Sabbia volcanic sandstones were related to the volcanic activity, possibly fed by subvolcanic intrusions similar to those of the study area (CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982).

(*) Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, Università degli Studi, Pisa, Italy.

(**) Dipartimento di Scienze Geologiche e Geotecnologie, Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca, Italy.

(***) CNR - Istituto per la Dinamica dei Processi Ambientali - Sezione di Milano, c/o Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, Via Mangiagalli, 34, 20133, Milano, Italy. gianluca.groppelli@unimi.it

(****) Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra «Ardito Desio», Università degli Studi, Milano, Italy.

Fig. 1 - Location of the studied area amongst the other Triassic subvolcanic and volcanic bodies of the Brescian Southern Alps (modified after CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982).

- Ubicazione dell'area studiata nel contesto dei corpi vulcanici e subvulcanici triassici delle Prealpi bresciane (modificato da CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982).

Based on detailed geological and structural field mapping by CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001), this paper presents the geochemical and petrological analyses of the magmatic rocks, in order to locate the subvolcanic bodies in the geodynamic context.

The lithostratigraphical nomenclature used in this paper results from the new stratigraphic methodologies and proposals for geological field mapping within a project of the National Prototype Geological Cartography (ARMIENTI *et alii*, 2000; CORAZZATO *et alii*, 2001).

STRATIGRAPHY

In this chapter we briefly describe the lithostratigraphical units of both the host rock and the subvolcanic bodies of the studied area, shown in the geological map of fig. 2, following the original survey at 1:5000 scale by CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001). For a detailed description of the host rock units and the Montecampione group subvolcanic units, refer to CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001), where they were recently defined.

HOST ROCK

The host rock lithostratigraphical units belong to an Upper Permian-Lower Triassic succession already well described in the literature. They consist of the Verrucano Lombardo and Servino formations (fig. 2), deposited over a palaeo-high of the Variscan basement («Val Trompia Ridge»; CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982; CASSINIS, 1985).

The Verrucano Lombardo formation (ASSERETO & CASATI, 1965; ORI *et alii*, 1986; CASSINIS, 1988; CASSINIS *et alii*, 1999 with references) in the study area is repre-

sented by clastic red beds, mainly composed of metre-thick banks of coarse sandstones with a fine sandstone matrix. Decimetre to metre-thick lenses are present: they are formed by fine to very coarse-grained conglomerates, finegrained sandstones and siltstones. Decimetre-sized quartz clasts, subordinate reddish clasts of alkali-feldspar and volcanic, metamorphic and silty lithics are observed, and concentrations of white micas are locally present. The maximum observed thickness for this unit in the studied area is 400 m. The Verrucano Lombardo crops out widely in the area (fig. 2) and rests non-conformably on the Variscan basement (BENCIOLINI *et alii*, 1999).

The Servino Formation (ASSERETO & CASATI, 1965; SCIUNNACH *et alii*, 1996; 1999; DE DONATIS & FALLETTI, 1999) is represented by a wide variety of lithotypes, comprising mature quartzose sandstones, mudstones, marls, sandstones and dolomitic siltstones, marly and oolitic limestones, and arkosic sandstones. In the study area the Servino Formation has a thickness of 100 m and rests in paraconformity on the Verrucano Lombardo.

SUBVOLCANIC UNITS - MONTECAMPIONE GROUP

The Montecampione group has recently been defined by CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001), and consists of magmatic bodies in the Montecampione area intruding into the Upper Permian-Lower Triassic sequence at different stratigraphic levels. They are mainly represented by laccoliths and sills, while some dykes are present in the outer zones of the studied area (fig. 2). These subvolcanic bodies were previously considered as a single unit and generically defined as «Triassic Porphyry of undefined age» in the Breno sheet at 1:100,000 scale (BIANCHI *et alii*, 1970; 1971) and «Porphyry of undefined age» in *Carta geologica delle Prealpi bresciane a sud dell'Adamello* (1972) at 1:50,000 scale. CASSINIS & ZEZZA (1982) identified the «dacitic laccolithic masses of Monte Muffetto, Dosso Sparviero and Corno Mura» and the «high-K andesitic sills of Beccheria di Bassinale», demonstrating a compositional range. CASSINIS (1988) described the «Porphyry» as the «subvolcanic mass of Corno Mura, with dacitic composition, Ladinian in age». BENCIOLINI (1996) and BENCIOLINI *et alii* (1999) defined the Monte Muffetto Lithosome, identifying four main laccoliths.

The subvolcanic bodies show variable thickness from a few centimetres to hundreds of metres, and extend from metres to kilometres. The stratigraphic relationships with the host rocks indicate that these subvolcanic bodies were emplaced after the deposition of the Servino Formation (Middle-Late Griesbachian to Early Spathian). Radiometric Rb/Sr dating available in the literature (CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982) supports absolute ages for Dosso Sparviero (226±4 Ma) and Monte Muffetto (231±5 Ma), ascribing them to the Middle-Late Triassic, particularly the Ladinian or Carnian (CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982), within the setting of the Southern Alps Triassic volcanism. This is demonstrated by widespread volcanic and subvolcanic products in two main horizons: Upper Anisian-Lower Ladinian and Ladinian-Carnian/Carnian, together with coeval pyroclastic layers interbedded in the sedimentary succession (PASQUARÈ & ROSSI, 1969) and volcanic sandstones (Arenaria di Val Sabbia).

In the simplified geological map of fig. 2 the subvolcanic bodies are organised on the basis of a detailed stratigraphical reconstruction. New lithostratigraphical units

Fig. 2 - Simplified geological map, with sample locations.
- Carta geologica semplificata, con riportate le ubicazioni dei campioni analizzati.

have been defined (CORAZZATO *et alii*, 2001) based on the lithology, geometry of the bodies, stratigraphic position, intersection and mutual deformation relationships between the bodies, and chemical composition (ARMIENTI *et alii*, 2000). The same criteria allowed the definition of some members within the units where it was possible to recognise variation of lesser rank: these members, defined and described in detail by CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001), can be related to different pulses within the intrusion of the main body. All the formational units comprise a lithostratigraphical unit of greater rank named the «Montecampione group» (CORAZZATO *et alii*, 2001). This group consists of the Monte Muffetto unit, the Corne di Regoia unit, the Dosso Sparviero unit and the La Paglia unit (fig. 2). A brief description of these units follows.

Monte Muffetto unit

This unit, defined by CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001), is located in the western and southwestern parts of the studied

area, over an extent of 3 km² (fig. 2). The main body, centred on the Monte Muffetto high, is a bell-shaped laccolith with many apophyses, and shows a maximum thickness of 350 m in correspondence with the southern slope of Monte Muffetto.

Apart from this main body, two members were distinguished (CORAZZATO *et alii*, 2001): the Alpiatz member and the Beccheria di Bassinale member, gathering a set of sills.

The magmatic rock, showing columnar jointing, has a porphyritic texture, with phenocrysts of quartz, pink feldspar, amphibole and biotite and diffuse mafic microcrystalline enclaves with a chemical and mineralogical composition similar to the dykes of the La Paglia unit (cf. «La Paglia unit»). The enclaves show an amoeboid aspect and exhibit different degrees of mingling with the host magma, thus showing that magma supply to the intrusion did not take place as a single pulse but through distinct magma batches; they are evidently linked with late magma pulses which fed the main intrusion. Within the

main intrusive body, broad lithological-petrographical variations are evident, encompassing all the characteristics of the members.

The chronological relationship between the Monte Muffetto unit and the more recent Corne di Regoia unit was inferred on the basis of a wide-scale deformation induced by the emplacement of the main body of Corne di Regoia on a sill of the Monte Muffetto unit cropping out NW of Valle delle Zoie at 1830 m a.s.l. (fig. 2): this sill is actually deformed together with the hosting sedimentary succession, while there is no evidence of Alpine tectonic deformation.

Corne di Regoia unit

This unit, defined by CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001), is represented by a magmatic body with a surface extent of 4 km², a length of 2.5 km in an E-W direction and more than 2 km N-S. It is the unit with the greatest extent in the studied area (fig. 2), although the outcropping part represents just the remnant northern part of the original body, the southern one being removed by erosion (in correspondence with the Corne di Regoia wall) and by the Monte Rosello structural lineament.

Apart from the main magmatic body, three lesser bodies defined as members (CORAZZATO *et alii*, 2001) were recognised within the unit: Corno Mura member, Bozzoline member and Cima Toricella member, a smaller bell-shaped laccolith located at the top of the main body. Its geometry and stratigraphic relations suggest that it intruded after the main body, probably using the same feeding conduit. These members show similar petrographical characteristics and a close genetic affinity, as can be inferred from their geometric-morphological relationships.

The magmatic rock, affected by columnar jointing, is pink-purple in colour and shows a porphyritic texture, phenocrysts of pink feldspar, amphibole, quartz and altered biotite, in a light grey-pink groundmass. Frequent mafic microcrystalline enclaves are observed within the Cima Toricella member, which is less porphyric.

The subvolcanic body cropping out in the central part of the area is affected by N-S fracturing in the central part of the valley, while the lateral portions are characterised by subhorizontal contact with the overhanging Verrucano Lombardo, uplifted and slightly tilted, cropping out in thin plates with opposite dip on the two sides of the laccolith. Apart from the erosion on the southern slope, the body was truncated towards the NE by the Monte Rosello structural lineament. It is not possible to know the original extent of the body toward the NE, nor its maximum thickness.

Dosso Sparviero unit

This unit, defined by CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001), crops out in the NW part of the studied area (fig. 2) in correspondence with the homonymous hill and in the valleys west of it, with a kilometric extension and a maximum thickness of 250 m. This unit comprises a magmatic rock with vertical columnar jointing, purple-dark grey in colour, with a porphyritic texture and abundant groundmass, white feldspar phenocrysts up to 2-3 mm, abundant phenocrysts of altered biotite, rare elongate amphibole crystals up to 5 mm long, and traces of zeolites in vacuoles.

The subvolcanic body shows a main laccolithic portion where the greatest thickness is recorded (fig. 3), and from which two sills depart westwards. No lithological difference occurs within the unit, that is very homogeneous.

The laccolith is bell-shaped and shows a N-S elongation and mainly vertical contacts. It forms steep walls on the eastern side of the hill (fig. 3); a thick debris talus at its base hides the contact with the Corne di Regoia unit, interpreted as vertical. On the ridge, the southern contact dips towards the south together with the overhanging sedimentary succession, which was arched during the emplacement of the body. The contact surface with the host rock at the top of the laccolith is sharp but with irregular protrusions, and it is discordant with the host rock bedding.

La Paglia unit

This unit, defined by CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001), links some bodies with limited extent and metre thickness, mostly dykes, found in the outer parts of the area, both in the Verrucano Lombardo and the Servino Formation. They consist of dark green magmatic rocks with a subaphyric texture, with biotite phenocrysts and rare vitric portions. Although not showing direct stratigraphic relations, they can be considered to follow the emplacement of the main subvolcanic bodies thanks to their compositional and mineralogical affinity with the mafic enclaves found in the Monte Muffetto unit.

PETROGRAPHY AND GEOCHEMISTRY OF THE SUBVOLCANIC BODIES

PETROGRAPHY

The Montecampione subvolcanic rocks exhibit mainly porphyritic textures, with a Porphyritic Index varying between 5% and 40%. Glomerophyric aggregates of plagioclase and amphibole are widespread and sometimes contain relicts of uralitised augite; groundmasses, usually microcrystalline, are devitrified or fine to very fine grained. Some samples from the Corne di Regoia unit contain spherulitic aggregates of quartz + chlorite, possible relicts of original vacuoles. The only holocrystalline, equigranular and finegrained textures are those observed in mafic enclaves of the Monte Muffetto unit and in some dykes of the La Paglia unit. Alteration is widespread and often pervasive, involving all mafic minerals, whose phenocrysts are frequently totally replaced by chlorite. The evolution degree varies from trachyandesite to trachyte; phenocrysts are dominated by zoned plagioclase in the range of andesitic compositions. More Ca-rich cores are altered to saussurite. In some samples with seriated textures (commonly among the sills of the Beccheria di Bassinale member), plagioclase phenocrysts represent 20% of the mode. Microcrystals of oligoclase are abundant in the groundmass, but sanidine is rare and is found as microphenocrysts only in sample CR6 (location in fig. 2). Although magmatic quartz phenocrysts can be as abundant as 5% (Corne di Regoia unit and some sills of the Beccheria di Bassinale member), they may be absent. They constantly exhibit resorption features; in the Corne di Regoia unit, mortar textures in some quartz crystals reveal their origin from the metamorphic basement. Quartz phenocrysts

crystallised from the magma may show peccilic inclusions of plagioclase crystals. The abundance of mafic minerals varies with the evolution degree: amphibole is always present, reaching the maximum size (5 mm) and the higher contents (up to 10% by volume) in the Corne di Regoia unit. The amount of biotite is also variable: although always occurring in the groundmass as unaltered microphenocrysts, when it occurs as phenocrysts it is constantly altered to chlorite. Biotite reaches the highest contents (10% of phenocrysts) in some mafic portions of the Monte Muffetto unit and in some dykes of the La Paglia unit.

Groundmasses exhibit quartz-feldspathic mineralogy, with widespread Ti-magnetite and goethite. In microcrystalline varieties the quartz/plagioclase ratio varies and the samples in which quartz is lacking have the greater abundance of intergranular mafic minerals (amphibole \pm biotite \pm augite). Albite is a widespread devitrification product in the groundmass. Apatite and zircon are ubiquitous accessory phases. Calcite patches or veins are always present, together with chlorite which replaces mafic minerals. Deuteric epidote is rare and is sporadically found in some dykes of the La Paglia unit showing weak autometamorphism (albite + chlorite + epidote).

GEOCHEMICAL ANALYSES

For a selection of less altered rocks, major (SiO_2 , TiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 , MnO , CaO , K_2O , P_2O_5) and trace (Ce, Ba, La, Ni, Cr, V, Co, Nb, Y, Sr, Rb) element analyses were performed by XRF, using a Philips Spectrometer-PW1480 and following the standardisation procedures proposed by FRANZINI *et alii* (1975) and LEONI & SAITTA (1976). For each sample (location in fig. 2) FeO was determined with the Wilson Titration method, LOI was measured using a Microwave Furnace (CEM, Ashing System - 300), and Na_2O and MgO by AAS following standard procedures (analyst M. Bertoli, Earth Science Department, Pisa University). A subset of samples has also been analysed by ICP-MS to determine concentrations of Sc, V, Cr, Co, Ni, Rb, Sr, Y, Zr, Nb, Cs, Ba, REEs, Hf, Ta, Pb, Th and U (analyst M. D'Orazio, Earth Science Department, Pisa University). Powdered rocks were dissolved by conventional HNO_3 + HF acid digestion, then spiked with Rh, Re and Bi (internal standards). Analytical precision, estimated by repeated analyses of geochemical reference samples, typically ranges from about 10% at 10 \times detection limit, to 3-5% at 100 \times detection limit; consequently, different numbers of significant figures are used to report results. The accuracy of data, evaluated by regularly analysing well-certified geochemical reference samples, typically ranges from 0 to 7% for elements at 50-100 \times detection limit.

Table 1 reports analytical data and CIPW norms; table 2 contains trace element abundances as determined by ICP-MS.

The adoption of the classification scheme of volcanic rocks for these subvolcanic intrusions is suggested by the prevalence of devitrified groundmass and by the shallow level of emplacement as revealed by relicts of vacuolar textures.

The whole association is affected by an evident alteration, marked by diffusion of deuteric chlorite and calcite, by the high values of the LOI (>2.4 wt%, table 1) and underlined by the frequent occurrence of normative corundum,

Fig. 3 - Southeastern side of the outcrop of the Dosso Sparviero unit subvolcanic body. Observed thickness is 250 m.
- Parete sud-orientale dell'affioramento del corpo subvolcanico appartenente all'unità Dosso Sparviero. Lo spessore osservato è 250 m.

caused by deuteric alkali loss. This implies that any classification scheme based on major elements is to be used with caution. For instance, in the alkali-silica diagram (TAS, LEMAÎTRE, 1989) the samples fall on the divides proposed by IRVINE & BARAGAR (1971) and KUNO (1966) between alkalic and sub-alkalic lavas (fig. 4). However, the low CaO content in most samples (table 1) indicates the pronounced mobility of this element, suggesting that alkalis too have been affected by similar deuteric depletion processes. In any case, the high total alkali content (>6 wt%) and high $\text{K}_2\text{O}/\text{Na}_2\text{O}$ ratios (often >1; table 1) suggest that these rocks belong to an alkaline association of high-K to shoshonitic affinity. This is confirmed by mineralogy, showing a widespread occurrence of biotite, and by the systematically low Nb/Y ratios (< 0.5, see table 2) (WINCHESTER & FLOID, 1977). Thus the chemical classification of these rocks has been simply based on the total alkali-silica diagram, adopting names of high rank in this classification scheme. In this respect the K_2O vs SiO_2 diagram would be redundant for classification purposes, since the amount of alkali loss suffered by rocks during alteration is unpredictable and that the names of shoshonitic rocks are provided on the basis of names of alkaline rocks in the total alkali-silica diagram (LEMAÎTRE, 1989). Fig. 4 reports the position of samples in the TAS diagram where they fall in the weakly alkaline field; the inset reports literature data (CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982) on the Trias magmatic rocks in nearby areas of the Brescian Alps, most of which show a transitional character. Our new data show that Montecampione group units are characterised by higher alkali contents than those found by CASSINIS & ZEZZA (1982) and fall in a range of silica values including the least evolved compositions of all the Brescian Alps, with Mg# in the interval 79-52. The recent survey of CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001) puts in evidence several members in the different units, each one linked to the emplacement of distinct magma batches supplied to the subvolcanic complex. The most evolved rocks turn out to be trachydacites of the Corne di Regoia unit, which, in turn, includes a member (Cima Toricella) consisting of a large mass of trachyan-desitic composition (Mg# =69).

The less evolved compositions in the whole association are, however, typically found among the mafic inclusions of the Monte Muffetto unit and the dykes of the La

TABLE 1

Major and trace elements for the Montecampione group.

SiO₂, TiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, MnO, CaO, K₂O, P₂O₅ and trace elements (Ce, Ba, La, Ni, Cr, V, Co, Nb, Y, Sr, Rb) were determined with the Wilson Titration method, LOI was determined using a Microwave Furnace. Na₂O and MgO by atomic absorption spectrometry. Mg# (FeO/(FeO+MgO), on molecular basis) and CIPW norms were computed adopting the FeO/Fe₂O₃ following from the procedure of MIDDLEMOST (1989). Sample locations in fig. 2.

Elementi maggiori e in tracce per il gruppo di Montecampione.

SiO₂, TiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, MnO, CaO, K₂O, P₂O₅ e gli elementi in tracce (Ce, Ba, La, Ni, Cr, V, Co, Nb, Y, Sr, Rb) sono ottenuti con XRF. FeO è stato determinato con il «Wilson Titration method». LOI è stato determinato usando una «Microwave Furnace». Na₂O e MgO sono stati determinati con «Atomic Absorption Spectrometry». Mg# (FeO/(FeO+MgO), su base molecolare) e le norme CIPW sono state calcolate adottando FeO/Fe₂O₃ secondo la procedura di MIDDLEMOST (1989). Ubicazioni dei campioni in fig. 2.

	Monte Muffetto unit				Dosso Sparviero unit				Corno di Regolia unit				La Paglia unit									
	MU 1	MU 2	MU 4	MU 7	MU 7b	MU 8	MU 9	MU 10	MU 11/i	MU 12	MU 14/i	DS 2	DS 3	CR 1	CR 3	CR 4	CR 5	CR 6	CR 79	LP 75	LP 106	
SiO ₂	61,98	63,35	61,58	61,67	62,93	61,84	63,70	63,84	51,92	62,80	55,45	61,91	64,56	58,06	64,72	64,43	64,02	63,98	57,97	60,62	59,46	
TiO ₂	0,62	0,57	0,69	0,59	0,56	0,63	0,55	0,60	0,87	0,49	0,96	0,56	0,54	0,71	0,51	0,49	0,53	0,53	1,27	0,99	1,15	
Al ₂ O ₃	16,05	15,88	16,08	15,79	16,24	15,98	16,45	16,08	18,18	15,81	17,19	16,97	16,56	16,74	16,40	16,32	13,13	16,36	16,94	15,27	16,28	
Fe ₂ O ₃	1,85	1,53	1,87	2,00	1,70	2,03	2,62	2,06	3,84	2,58	2,31	2,35	2,04	2,57	1,55	2,00	1,54	1,33	5,89*	4,44*	6,24*	
FeO	3,56	3,42	3,09	3,81	3,52	3,44	2,32	3,23	6,75	2,51	6,93	3,69	2,98	3,70	3,29	3,00	3,32	3,12				
MnO	0,05	0,14	0,04	0,08	0,07	0,07	0,28	0,31	0,46	0,33	0,23	0,14	0,08	0,21	0,08	0,10	0,08	0,05	0,15	0,14	0,18	
MgO	3,20	3,26	4,10	3,21	2,54	3,09	2,18	2,34	4,86	1,93	5,16	2,38	1,89	4,09	1,97	2,12	2,20	3,62	4,91	5,92	4,06	
CaO	0,95	0,47	0,71	1,20	1,35	1,30	0,75	1,21	0,39	1,30	0,40	1,06	0,51	3,00	0,49	0,45	0,67	0,29	1,04	1,83	1,28	
Na ₂ O	3,93	4,45	3,15	3,86	3,89	4,32	4,56	3,92	4,72	4,74	4,36	3,96	3,76	3,73	4,48	5,16	4,87	4,18	1,39	3,27	4,94	
K ₂ O	4,38	4,05	5,21	4,12	3,76	3,92	3,67	3,76	3,12	4,37	2,10	3,25	4,36	3,15	3,54	3,17	3,65	3,07	6,93	4,19	3,38	
P ₂ O ₅	0,20	0,21	0,21	0,20	0,23	0,21	0,24	0,25	0,27	0,22	0,30	0,23	0,22	0,25	0,22	0,22	0,21	0,20	0,31	0,28	0,27	
LOI	3,22	2,68	3,28	3,46	3,20	3,17	2,69	2,40	4,63	2,69	4,61	3,52	2,51	3,79	2,78	2,54	2,78	3,27	3,20	3,05	2,77	
Mg#	61,28	63,72	68,95	59,66	56,52	60,26	54,64	54,33	53,58	50,80	58,13	51,45	50,35	62,25	52,08	53,30	54,71	67,03	69,19	79,29	63,67	
Trace elements by XRF (ppm)																						
Ce			61	76	68				93			61						61				
Ba			444	422	351				303			457						194				
La			31	38	34				49			36						35				
Ni			8	5	7				8			5						7				
Cr			19	10	22				11			10						8				
V			99	77	109				172			76						74				
Co			14	12	13				32			12						11				
Nb			9	9	8				11			9						9				
Y			24	27	20				20			32						25				
Sr			46	93	73				135			83						46				
Rb			135	144	137				128			167						151				
CIPW Norms																						
Q	14,68	15,26	15,13	15,05	18,58	13,40	17,52	19,67	0,34	11,75	10,83	19,67	21,44	10,21	20,53	17,37	16,80	21,34	13,33	12,88	7,89	
C	3,72	3,93	4,62	3,40	3,99	2,86	4,31	4,06	7,32	1,49	8,11	5,76	5,39	2,43	4,97	4,22	0,48	6,32	6,23	2,79	2,91	
or	26,75	24,59	31,84	25,22	22,95	23,93	22,31	22,77	19,35	26,63	13,00	19,91	26,44	19,36	21,51	19,23	22,89	18,76	42,50	25,62	20,64	
ab	34,37	38,68	27,56	33,84	34,01	37,76	39,69	34,00	41,91	41,35	38,66	34,74	32,64	32,83	38,98	44,82	43,73	36,57	12,21	28,63	43,19	
an	3,52	0,99	2,22	4,82	5,37	5,25	2,22	4,48	0,18	5,17	0,03	3,90	1,12	13,78	1,02	0,82	2,07	0,14	3,25	7,50	4,74	
-en	8,24	8,34	10,56	8,28	6,54	7,95	5,58	5,97	12,70	4,96	13,47	6,14	4,83	10,60	5,04	5,42	5,81	9,32	12,69	15,26	10,45	
-fs	4,34	4,14	3,74	4,85	4,30	4,40	4,32	4,69	11,24	4,69	9,24	5,22	4,09	6,11	4,01	4,20	4,13	4,20	4,20	2,63	4,81	
hy	12,57	12,48	14,30	13,13	10,83	12,35	9,91	10,66	23,95	9,64	22,71	11,36	8,92	16,71	9,06	9,61	9,95	13,45	16,89	17,89	15,25	
mt	2,70	2,46	2,47	2,91	2,61	2,72	2,40	2,60	4,57	2,49	4,03	3,01	2,47	2,67	2,41	2,46	2,50	1,90	2,35	2,07	2,47	
il	1,22	1,11	1,35	1,16	1,10	1,24	1,07	1,17	1,73	0,96	1,91	1,10	1,05	1,40	1,00	0,96	1,07	1,04	2,50	1,94	2,26	
ap	0,48	0,50	0,50	0,48	0,55	0,50	0,57	0,59	0,66	0,53	0,73	0,55	0,52	0,60	0,52	0,52	0,52	0,48	0,75	0,64	0,65	

* = Fe₂O₃ tot

/= Mafic inclusion

T=Trachyte, TA=Trachyandesite, TD=Trachydacite, D=Dacite;

Mg# calculated with Fe₂O₃/FeO according to Middlemost (1989).

TABLE 2

ICP-MS trace element analyses for the Montecampione group.

Analyst Massimo D'Orazio, DST - Pisa. Sample locations in fig. 2.

Analisi ICP-MS degli elementi in tracce del gruppo di Montecampione. Analista Massimo D'Orazio, DST - Pisa. Ubicazioni dei campioni in fig. 2.

	Monte Muffetto unit							Dozzo Sp. u.	Corne di Regoia unit			
	MU 1	MU 2	MU 4	MU 9	MU 10	MU 12	MU 14/i	DS2	CR1	CR 3	CR 4	CR 5
	T	T	T	T	T	T	TA	T	TA	TD	T	T
Sc	14	12	14	11	10	11	22	12	20	10	10	10
V	103	73	108	70	69	69	155	81	143	63	62	67
Cr	18	9	19	8	10	19	17	7	37	6	6	5
Co	10	7	9	6	8	8	16	7	13	7	7	7
Ni	6	3	6	3	3	4	6	4	11	4	3	2
Rb	131	142	130	142	152	130	95	156	108	134	108	123
Sr	55	99	29	282	346	81	72	94	339	73	67	41
Y	25.3	30.8	24.4	32.0	27.3	23.4	22.2	26.0	28.8	27.7	25.1	28.8
Zr	77	72	83	56	58	54	65	51	118	62	61	64
Nb	8.1	8.7	7.4	8.7	9.0	8.3	10.1	9.4	7.6	9.2	9.5	8.9
Mo	1.5	1.7	1.4	1.9	1.7	0.8	1.4	1.6	2.0	1.7	1.8	1.9
Cs	6.7	4.7	3.6	3.3	4.4	2.26	10.3	12.2	9.8	9.1	5.8	5.8
Ba	337	1038	507	722	755	439	137	260	584	360	388	313
La	35	36	33	48	39	31	33	34	34	42	39	39
Ce	70	75	67	95	79	64	58	73	70	83	74	74
Pr	8.1	8.9	7.8	11.2	9.2	7.8	7.8	9.0	8.5	10.3	8.9	9.1
Nd	29.8	32.8	29.1	42	34	29.6	30.1	33.2	32.4	38	33.3	32.2
Sm	5.7	6.6	5.4	8.2	6.5	5.9	6.2	6.3	6.6	7.2	6.5	6.5
Eu	1.37	1.41	1.06	1.61	1.27	1.28	1.48	1.15	1.71	1.43	1.4	1.34
Gd	4.4	6.0	4.7	6.6	5.6	4.8	5.0	4.8	5.5	5.6	5.1	5.4
Tb	0.69	0.95	0.7	0.98	0.83	0.71	0.74	0.77	0.83	0.85	0.76	0.82
Dy	4.3	5.6	4.3	6.1	4.8	4.1	4.1	4.3	4.9	5.0	4.5	4.8
Ho	0.85	1.06	0.83	1.12	0.96	0.8	0.77	0.81	1.04	0.96	0.84	0.96
Er	2.34	2.81	2.39	2.92	2.57	2.10	2.03	2.14	2.84	2.68	2.37	2.53
Tm	0.38	0.43	0.38	0.47	0.41	0.34	0.33	0.33	0.44	0.42	0.36	0.40
Yb	2.21	2.81	2.42	2.67	2.4	2.05	2.03	1.87	2.56	2.42	2.18	2.39
Lu	0.35	0.37	0.37	0.40	0.36	0.32	0.31	0.28	0.38	0.38	0.33	0.36
Hf	2.28	2.25	2.59	1.90	1.82	1.71	1.95	1.52	3.19	1.95	1.96	1.90
Ta	0.68	0.72	0.64	0.73	0.73	0.70	0.69	0.71	0.54	0.75	0.74	0.72
Tl	1.20	0.70	1.11	0.75	0.78	1.06	0.50	0.86	1.01	1.08	0.86	0.76
Pb	4.0	51	5.7	40	70	29.0	2.7	4.5	27.49	5.2	4.3	2.3
Th	12.27	10.7	11.17	13.3	12.2	13.8	7.5	11.0	8.8	13.2	10.1	11.1
U	2.31	2.03	2.08	2.21	2.31	2.20	1.50	2.06	1.56	2.09	2.09	2.06
Th/Ta	18.0	14.8	17.5	18.2	16.7	19.7	10.9	15.5	16.3	17.5	13.7	15.4
Zr/Hf	33.7	31.9	32.0	29.3	31.8	31.3	33.5	33.33	37.1	31.6	31.3	33.7

T=Trachyte, TA=Trachyandesite, TD=Trachydacite; /i= Mafic inclusion.

Paglia unit, which are similar in petrographical features, although much more altered. The two analysed samples of La Paglia unit dykes fall astride the subdivision trachyandesite-trachyte (fig. 4).

The pervasive alteration introduces some ambiguity into the interpretation of the major element correlation diagrams: the negative correlation in Harker diagrams (fig. 5) of CaO and K₂O for SiO₂ >60% could be due both to massive plagioclase and biotite fractionation and/or to deuteric mobilisation of these elements. On the other hand the same rocks exhibit a positive correlation of Na₂O with SiO₂ that conflicts with fractionation of andesinic plagioclase, thus suggesting that the observed trends of CaO, K₂O and Na₂O in Harker diagrams are due to alteration. The late occurrence of the pulses of

less evolved magma hinders the hypothesis of a direct petrogenetic link between the trachyandesites and more evolved rocks due to crystal fractionation, this being confirmed by the lack of correlation in the variation diagrams between incompatible immobile elements like Th, Ta, Hf and Nb (fig. 5), whose original abundance is not changed by alteration processes. In these diagrams, rocks with similar degrees of evolution practically overlap within the analytical error, while less evolved magmas represent completely different magma batches with respect to the main mass of the subvolcanic complex (fig. 5). Although Zr and Nb are not mobilised during deuteric alteration, the widespread occurrence of hornblende and zircon causes their fractionation (fig. 5, SiO₂ vs Zr and Nb vs Th diagrams), hindering their utilisation as incom-

Fig. 4 - TAS diagram for the Montecampione group. The inset reports only literature data (CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982) for Triassic magmatic rocks of the Brescian Southern Alps. Black dots in the inset are literature Montecampione (Mt. Muffetto) rocks. The grey area of the inset corresponds to the enlarged field where only the new geochemical data provided in this work are reported.

- *Diagramma TAS per il gruppo di Montecampione. L'inserito riporta solo i dati di letteratura (CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982) per il magmatismo triassico delle Prealpi Bresciane. I cerchi neri nell'inserito sono relativi ai dati di letteratura per le rocce di Montecampione. L'area in grigio corrisponde al campo ingrandito, in cui sono rappresentati solo i punti relativi ai campioni studiati in questo lavoro.*

patible elements with a key role in most discrimination diagrams.

For this reason the evaluation of the geochemical affinity is to be based on multi-elemental normalisation diagrams. The chondrite-normalised distributions (fig. 6) of rare earth elements (REEs) of analysed rocks are light REE (LREE) enriched ($LaN \approx 150-200$), with LaN/YbN varying between 9 and 12. Surprisingly, negative Eu anomalies are very small ($Eu/Eu^* \approx 0.6$) or practically absent: this implies that, in spite of the abundance of plagioclase, this mineral suffered only weak fractionation and was not a cumulus phase. The absence of Eu anomalies in some of the less evolved, poorly porphyritic rocks implies evolution before the appearance of plagioclase on the liquidus and is consistent with their high Mg#. This allows us to consider most of the samples as representative of magmatic liquid and to infer some information from multi-elemental normalised diagrams, in order to understand the possible origin of the association. The general distribution of incompatible elements (fig. 7) is dominated by low ratios of high field strength elements (HFSEs: Nb, Ta, Hf, Zr, Ti) to large-ion lithophile elements (LILEs) and Y-heavy REE (HREE), as revealed by negative anomalies in the N-MORB normalised multi-elemental diagrams. These features are typical of subduction zone magmatism and allow their distinction from alkaline intraplate magmas (SUN & MCDONOUGH, 1989). The overall enrichment in LREEs and LILEs (Rb, K, Cs) is the fingerprint of a back-arc setting, usually associated with the great depths reached by the

subducting slab in volcanic arc magmatism (TATSUMI & EGGINS, 1995).

Thus, in spite of the pervasive alteration mobilising alkalis and Ca, the other geochemical features of this association of subvolcanic rocks allows them to be classified among the high-K to shoshonitic series.

THE MONTECAMPIONE GROUP SUBVOLCANIC BODIES IN THE GEODYNAMIC FRAMEWORK

Based on detailed geological and structural field mapping by CORAZZATO *et alii* (2001), this paper presents the geochemical and petrological analyses of the magmatic rocks, in order to locate the subvolcanic bodies in the geodynamic framework.

Assessment of the emplacement depth of the Montecampione units benefits from information reported in the literature for adjacent areas (ASSERETO & CASATI, 1965) about the sedimentary succession overlying the Servino Formation in the Ladinian-Carnian (the radiometric Rb/Sr ages available in the literature being 226 ± 4 Ma and 231 ± 5 Ma for the Dosso Sparviero and Monte Muffetto units respectively: CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982). An average value of 1000 m can be considered the best estimate of the emplacement depth.

As part of the Triassic volcanism in the Brescian area, the Montecampione group subvolcanic bodies could thus be regarded as shallow magma chambers that fed a volcanic edifice, as witnessed by some probable magmatic conduits recognised in the field. The erosion of the volcano could have supplied most of the detritus forming the Arenaria di Val Sabbia volcanic sandstone (CASSINIS & ZEZZA, 1982; GARZANTI, 1988). NATOLI (2000) computed using a GIS that the minimum volume for the preserved portions of the shallow magmatic reservoir represented by the subvolcanic bodies is about 1 km^3 .

Different hypotheses have been discussed about the geodynamic setting for the Middle-Late Triassic magmatism of the Southern Alps. MARINELLI *et alii* (1980) suggested a back-arc basin environment; LUCCHINI *et alii* (1982) recognised a calc-alkaline-shoshonitic affinity for the Middle Triassic volcanics of the Southern Alps and, together with CASTELLARIN *et alii* (1988), suggested a subduction environment related to the closure of the Palaeo-tethys, rejecting the hypothesis of continental rifting. CASSINIS & ZEZZA (1982) supported an «orogenic-type» magmatism. JADOUËL & ROSSI (1982) discussed different models and related the volcanism to a tectonic uplift phase. FERRARA & INNOCENTI (1974) and BECHSTÄDT *et alii* (1978) suggested that an alkaline composition could be related to rifting, in which volcanic activity would be related to lithospheric extension. CRISCI *et alii* (1984), although recognising the calc-alkaline affinity of the Middle Triassic volcanic products in the Southern Alps, with characteristics similar to those of continental margins, explained the contrast between the type of magmas formed in an extensional tectonic environment during the Middle Triassic, and those from partial melting during the early stage of rifting of an upper mantle deeply modified during the previous Hercynian orogeny, and then contaminated by crustal material.

The geochemical features of this association of subvolcanic rocks classifies them among the high-K to shosh-

Fig. 5 - Variation diagrams for Na₂O, CaO, K₂O, P₂O₅ and Zr vs SiO₂, and Ta, Nb and La vs Th; XRF major element data from table 1. Trace element ICP-MS data from table 2.
 - Diagrammi di variazione per Na₂O, CaO, K₂O, P₂O₅ e Zr vs SiO₂, e Ta, Nb e La vs Th; Dati XRF degli elementi maggiori come da table 1. Dati ICP-MS degli elementi in traccia come da table 2.

Fig. 6 - Chondrite-normalised patterns for rare earth elements of the Montecampione group. REEs are normalised to the C1 chondrite (MCDONOUGH & SUN, 1995). Eu anomalies are absent or weak, up to a maximum value of $Eu/Eu^* = 0.6$.

- Pattern normalizzati alla condrite per gli elementi delle REE del gruppo di Montecampione. Le REE sono normalizzate alla condrite C1 (MCDONOUGH & SUN, 1995). Le anomalie di Eu sono assenti o deboli, raggiungendo al massimo un valore di $Eu/Eu^* = 0.6$.

Fig. 7 - Multi-element diagram for the Montecampione group. All element concentrations are normalised to the values of N-MORB (SUN & MCDONOUGH, 1989). The negative anomalies of Ta, Nb, Zr and Ti are typical of calc-alkaline associations.

- Diagramma multielementi per il gruppo di Montecampione. Tutte le concentrazioni degli elementi sono normalizzate ai valori degli N-Morb (SUN & MCDONOUGH, 1989). Le anomalie negative di Ta, Nb, Zr e Ti sono tipiche di associazioni calcalkaline.

onitic series. In spite of widespread alteration, high-quality geochemical data on immobile elements gathered in this study for the Montecampione units appear to be typical of subduction zone magmatism. Trace elements are in fact characterised by low ratios of Nb-Ta and other high field strength elements to LILEs and Y-HREEs. These features allow their distinction from alkaline intraplate magmas (SUN & McDONOUGH, 1989) which would be linked to the widespread lithospheric extension required by rifting processes. On the other hand, the pronounced enrichment in LREEs and LILEs (fig. 7) is usually considered indicative of a back-arc setting associated with the great depth achieved by the subducting slab (TATSUMI & EGGINS, 1995). Thus the geodynamic setting suggested by the geochemical features of the subvolcanic bodies, their shallow emplacement level, and the almost coeval deposition of volcanic sandstones in the nearby Val Sabbia Basin, could fit the setting of a back-arc, limited extension phase related to the subduction of a Palaeotethyan ocean during the early phases of the Cimmerian orogeny (STAMPFLI, 1996, 2000 and references; ZIEGLER & STAMPFLI, 2001; MUTTONI *et alii*, 2000 and references). An extension of the geochemical data-set with data of similar quality for the Triassic magmatism of the Brescian Alps would better constrain this hypothesis, defining the region and the time span over which back-arc extension was active.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge Cristiano Larghi, Dario Sciunnach, Cristina Bigoni and Laura Marinoni for their fruitful discussions and suggestions during the fieldwork, and Azienda Regionale delle Foreste-Ufficio Operativo di Breno (Brescia), Cooperativa Exodus in Sònico (Brescia) and Rifugio Alpini (Monte Cimoscio) for their assistance and logistical support. We wish to thank Giuseppe Cassinis and Luciano Cortesogno for their constructive suggestions and careful reviews of the manuscript. Samantha Jones improved the English style.

The research was funded by the Accordo di Programma SGN-CNR within the Prototype Geological Map Project, and C.C. benefited from a contract on these funds. The research was also supported by CNR-Agenzia 2000 Giovani (CNRG00F2A7).

REFERENCES

- ARMIENTI P., CORAZZATO C., GROPELLI G., NATOLI E. & PASQUARÈ G. (2000) - *I corpi subvolcanici triassici del Sudalpino centrale (Val Camonica-Val Trompia)*. Relazione finale Accordo di Programma tra CNR e SGN. Progetto Cartografia Prototipale, 17 pp.
- ASSERETO R. & CASATI P. (1965) - *Revisione della stratigrafia permotriassica della Valle Camonica meridionale*. Riv. It. Paleont. Strat., **71**, 999-1097.
- BECHSTÄDT T., BRANDNER R., MOSTLER H. & SCHMIDT K. (1978) - *Aborted rifting in the Triassic of the eastern and southern Alps*. Soc. Geol. Palaont. Abhandl., **2**, 157-178.
- BENCIOLINI L. (1996) - *Le geometrie dei corpi subvolcanici del Triassico medio nel Sudalpino Centrale (Val Camonica-Val Trompia)*. Atti Soc. Tosc. Sci. Nat., Mem., Serie A, **103**, 173-179.
- BENCIOLINI L., PASQUARÈ F.A. & PASQUARÈ G. (1999) - *Studio dei contatti fra corpi subvolcanici del Triassico medio e rocce sedimentarie incassanti nel Sudalpino Centrale (Valcamonica-Val Trompia)*. In Orombelli G. Ed., Studi geografici e geologici in onore di Severino Belloni. Univ. Studi Milano. Univ. Studi Milano-Bicocca. Glauco Brigati, Genova, 19-34.
- BIANCHI A., BONI A., CALLEGARI E., CASATI P., CASSINIS G., COMIZOLI G., DAL PIAZ G.B., DESIO A., GIUSEPPETTI G., MARTINA E., PASSERI L.D., SASSI F.P., ZANETTIN B. & ZIRPOLI G. (1970) - *Carta Geologica d'Italia alla scala 1:100.000. Foglio 34 - Breno*.
- BIANCHI A., BONI A., CALLEGARI E., CASATI P., CASSINIS G., COMIZOLI G., DAL PIAZ G.B., DESIO A., GIUSEPPETTI G., MARTINA E., PASSERI L.D., SASSI F.P., ZANETTIN B. & ZIRPOLI G. (1971) - *Note Illustrative della Carta Geologica d'Italia alla scala 1:100.000. Foglio 34 - Breno*. Ministero Industria, Roma, 134 pp.
- BONI A. & CASSINIS G. (1973) - *Carta geologica delle Prealpi Bresciane a Sud dell'Adamello. Note illustrative della legenda stratigrafica*. Atti Ist. Geol. Univ. Pavia, **23**, 119-159.
- Carta geologica delle Prealpi Bresciane a Sud dell'Adamello (1972) - Scala 1:50.000*. Istituto di Geologia dell'Università di Pavia. Atti Ist. Geol. Univ. Pavia, **23**.
- CASSINIS G. (1985) - *Il Permiano nel gruppo dell'Adamello, alla luce delle ricerche sui coevi terreni delle aree contermini*. Mem. Soc. Geol. It., **26**, 119-132.
- CASSINIS G. (1988) - *Carta geologica dei depositi continentali permiani a Sud dell'Adamello*. Atti Ticinensi Sci. Terra, **31**, Tav. I.
- CASSINIS G. & ZEZZA U. (1982) - *Dati geologici e petrografici sui prodotti del magmatismo triassico nelle Prealpi Bresciane*. In Castellarin A. & Vai G.B. Eds., Guida alla Geologia del Sudalpino centro-orientale. Guide Geol. Reg. S.G.I., 157-171.
- CASSINIS G., CORTESOGNO L., GAGGERO L., MASSARI F., NERI C., NICOSIA U. & PITTAU P. (COORDINATORS) (1999) - *Stratigraphy and facies of the Permian deposits between Eastern Lombardy and the Western Dolomites, Field Trip Guidebook*. «The continental Permian International Congress», 15-25 settembre 1999, Brescia, Italy. Earth Science Dept., Pavia University, 157 pp.
- CASTELLARIN A., LUCCHINI F., ROSSI P.L., SELLI L. & SIMBOLI G. (1988) - *The middle Triassic magmatic-tectonic arc development in the southern Alps*. Tectonophysics, **146**, 79-89.
- CORAZZATO C., GROPELLI G., NATOLI E. & PASQUARÈ G. (2001) - *Il gruppo di Montecampione: stratigrafia dei corpi subvolcanici triassici tra la Val Camonica e la Val Trompia*. Atti Tic. Sci. Terra, Pavia, **42**, 141-152.
- CRISCI G.M., FERRARA G., MAZZUOLI R. & ROSSI P.M. (1984) - *Geochemical and Geochronological Data on Triassic Volcanism of the Southern Alps of Lombardy (Italy): Genetic Implications*. Geol. Rundschau, **73**, 279-292.
- DE DONATIS S. & FALLETTI P. (1999) - *The Early Triassic Servino Formation of the Monte Guglielmo area and relationships with the Servino di Trompia and Camonica Valleys (Brescian Prealps, Lombardy)*. In Gosso G., Jadoul F., Sella M. & Spalla M.I. Eds., 3rd Workshop on Alpine Geological Studies. Biella-Oropa, September 29th-October 1st 1997, Mem. Sci. Geol. Padova, **51**, 91-101.
- FERRARA G. & INNOCENTI F. (1974) - *Radiometric age evidences of a thermal event in the Southern Alps*. Geol. Rundschau, **63**, 572-581.
- FRANZINI M., LEONI L. & SAITTA M. (1975) - *Revisione di una metodologia analitica per fluorescenza-X, basata sulla correzione completa degli effetti di matrice*. Rend. Soc. It. Miner. Petrol., **31**, 365-378.
- GARZANTI E. (1988) - *Ambienti sedimentari fluvio-deltizi e composizione petrografica: le arenarie del Trias Superiore lombardo*. Giorn. Geol., ser. 3, **50**, 163-165.
- IRVINE T.N. & BARAGAR W.R.A. (1971) - *A guide to the chemical classification of common volcanic rocks*. Can. J. Earth Sci., **8**, 523-548.
- JADOUL F. & ROSSI P.M. (1982) - *Evoluzione paleogeografico-strutturale e vulcanismo triassico nella Lombardia centro-occidentale*. In Castellarin A. & Vai G.B. Eds., Guida alla Geologia del Sudalpino centro-orientale. Guide Geol. Reg. S.G.I., 143-155.
- KUNO H. (1966) - *Lateral variation of basalt magma type across continental margins and island arcs*. Bull. Volcanol., **29**, 195-222.
- LEMAITRE R.W. (1989) - *A classification of igneous rocks and glossary of terms*. Oxford, Blackwell Scientific Publication, 193 pp.
- LEONI L. & SAITTA M. (1976) - *X-ray fluorescence analyses of 29 trace elements in rock and mineral standard*. Rend. Soc. It. Miner. Petrol., **32**, 497-510.
- LUCCHINI F., ROSSI P.M.L., SIMBOLI G. & CRISTOFOLINI R. (1982) - *Confronto geochimico fra i prodotti magmatici basici del Trias-Giura nell'area Tetidea*. In Castellarin A. & Vai G.B. Eds., Guida alla Geologia del Sudalpino centro-orientale. Guide Geol. Reg. S.G.I., 133-141.
- MARINELLI M., VIEL G. & FARABEGOLI E. (1980) - *Il Permo-Triassico delle Alpi Meridionali: evoluzione tardo ercinica di un bacino marginale di retroarco sialico*. L'Industria Mineraria, **6**, 1-11.
- MCDONOUGH W.F. & SUN S.S. (1995) - *The composition of the Earth*. Chem. Geol., **120**, 223-253.

- MIDDLEMOST E.A.K. (1989) - *Iron oxidation ratio, norms and the classification of volcanic rocks*. Chem. Geol., **77**, 19-26.
- MUTTONI G., GAETANI M., BUDUROV K., ZAGORCHEV I., TRIFONOVA E., IVANOVA D., PETROUNOVA L. & LOWRIE W. (2000) - *Middle Triassic data from northern Bulgaria: constraints on Tethyan magnetostratigraphy and paleogeography*. Palaeogeogr., Palaeoclim., Palaeoecol., **160**, 223-237.
- NATOLI E. (2000) - *Rilevamento geologico e analisi dei corpi subvulcanici di Montecampione (BS): metodologie e proposte finalizzate al progetto CARG*. Unpublished Thesis, Università degli Studi di Milano.
- ORI G.G., DALLA S. & CASSINIS G. (1986) - *Depositional history of the Permian continental sequence in the Valtrompia-Passo Croce Domini area (Brescian Alps, Italy)*. In Cassinis G. Ed., Proceedings of the field conference on: Permian and Permian-Triassic boundary in the Western Tethys, and additional regional reports. Brescia 4-12 July 1986. Mem. Soc. Geol. It., **34**, 141-154.
- PASQUARÈ G. & ROSSI P.M. (1969) - *Stratigrafia degli orizzonti piroclastici medio-triassici del Gruppo delle Grigne (Prealpi Lombarde)*. Riv. It. Pal. Strat., **75**, 1-87.
- SCIUNNACH D., GARZANTI E. & CONFALONIERI M.P. (1996) - *Stratigraphy and petrography of Upper Permian to Anisian terrigenous wedges (Verrucano Lombardo, Servino and Bellano Formations; Western Southern Alps)*. Riv. It. Paleont. Strat., **102** (1), 27-48.
- SCIUNNACH D., GARZANTI E., POSENATO R. & RODEGHIERO F. (1999) - *Stratigraphy of the Servino Formation (Lombardy, Southern Alps) towards a refined correlation with the Werfen Formation of the Dolomites*. In Gosso G., Jadoul F., Sella M. & Spalla M.I. Eds., 3rd Workshop on Alpine Geological Studies. Biella-Oropa, September 29th-October 1st 1997. Mem. Sc. Geol. Padova, **51** (1), 103-118.
- STAMPFLI G.M. (1996) - *The Intra-Alpine Terrane: A Palaeotethyan remnant in the Alpine Variscides*. Eclogae Geol. Helv., **89** (1), 13-42
- STAMPFLI G.M. (2000) - *Tethyan oceans*. In Bozkurt E., Winchester J.A. & Piper J.D.A. Eds. Tectonics and Magmatism in Turkey and the Surrounding Area. Geol. Soc. London, Spec. Publ., **173**, 1-23.
- SUN S.S. & McDONOUGH W.F. (1989) - *Chemical and isotopic systematics of oceanic basalts: implications for mantle composition and processes*. In Saunders A.D. & Norry M.J. Eds., Magmatism in Ocean Basins. Geol. Soc. London Spec. Publ., **42**, 313-345.
- TATSUMI Y. & EGGINS S. (1995) - *Subduction zone magmatism*. Oxford, Blackwell Science Inc., 211 pp.
- WINCHESTER J.A. & FLOYD P.A. (1977) - *Geochemical discrimination of different magma series and their differentiation products using immobile elements*. Chem. Geol., **20**, 325-343.
- ZIEGLER P.A. & STAMPFLI G.M. (2001) - *Late Palaeozoic-Early Mesozoic plate boundary reorganisation: collapse of the Variscan orogen and opening of the Neothethys*. In Cassinis G. Ed., Permian continental deposits of Europe and other areas. Regional reports and correlations. Natura Bresciana, Ann. Mus. Civ. Sc. Nat., Brescia, Monografia, **25**, 17-34.

Manoscritto pervenuto il 18 Febbraio 2002; testo approvato per la stampa il 5 Agosto 2002; ultime bozze restituite il 14 Maggio 2003.